

Exploring the crosstalk between Sialyl-Tn (STn) expression and the progression of pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC)

Ana C. F. Soares^{1,2}, Mireia Castillo-Martin³, Rita Adubeiro Lourenço^{1,2}, Daniela Pinto^{1,2}, Paula A. Videira^{1,2}

¹ UCIBIO - Applied Molecular Biosciences Unit, Department of Life Sciences, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Caparica, Portugal

² Associate Laboratory i4HB - Institute for Health and Bioeconomy, NOVA School of Science and Technology, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal.

³ Champalimaud Foundation, Lisbon, Portugal

acf.soares@campus.fct.unl.pt; p.videira@fct.unl.pt

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Introduction: Pancreatic cancer (PC) is expected to become the second-leading cause of cancer-related deaths in the next decade ⁽¹⁾. The most common and deadliest form of PC derives from the exocrine pancreas being designated pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) ⁽²⁾. Since an efficient target treatment does not exist, surgery is currently the most successful clinical treatment. Yet, these patients have a low long-term survival rate ⁽³⁾. Therefore, new therapeutic targets are needed to surpass this limitation. Sialyl-Tn (STn) is a carbohydrate antigen that results from incomplete synthesis of branched O-glycan chains, mostly due to overexpression of sialyltransferase ST6GalNAc1⁽⁴⁾. This short sialylated O-glycan is associated with poor prognosis and immunosuppressive microenvironment since it contributes to cancer progression and metastasis ^{(4),(5)}. While PDAC is known to over-express truncated O-glycans ⁽⁶⁾, the STn profiling and role in different PC stages is elusive. Herein, we aim to investigate STn's impact in PDAC progression, elucidating its role as a possible therapeutic target.

Materials and Methods: An immunohistochemistry assay was conducted to evaluate the STn expression in 186 human pancreatic cancer tissues in different stages. The cohort included treated and untreated PDAC surgery samples, metastases samples, and precursor lesions samples such as intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasm (IPMN) and pancreatic intraepithelial neoplasia (PanIN). STn expression quantification was made using the H-score, considering the apical and cytoplasmic staining intensity and excluding the expression in the mucus.

Results: In our cohort, the normal pancreas rarely expressed STn antigen. The majority of the stained PDAC cases without treatment stained positive for STn and presented high expression. The PDAC post-chemotherapy cases showed a slight decrease in STn expression and IPMN precursor lesions revealed high heterogeneity in the staining. The high-grade dysplasia PanIN precursor lesion presented higher STn expression intensity when compared to low-grade dysplasia PanINs. The metastasis in lung, diaphragm, and liver, also presented high STn expression, except for one case in the liver. Furthermore, PC as well as other cancer cells human cell lines overexpressing ST6GalNAc1 showed

prominent expression of STn suggesting the aberrant expression of this enzyme as causative of STn aberrant expression.

Discussion: These results highlight the tumour specificity of STn and suggests a role for STn in cancer progression. Our data will enable correlation of STn with clinical features, and gene expression that may be common to other cancer types. Furthermore, we aim to validate STn-related immunophenotype from this cohort and then proceed to an *in vivo* mouse model and finally test anti-STn antibodies' efficacy in overcoming immunosuppression and reducing tumour progression using an *in vitro* model.

Conclusion: STn expression shows tumour specificity in PC, increasing from pre-malignant to malignant types and increased in metastatic lesions, suggesting its potential role in disease progression.

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